

The System of Medical Institutions Governance and its Role in Improving the Medical Services Quality: Evidence from Benghazi Medical Center

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Abstract

this paper aimed at shedding light on the impact of the corporate governance system on improving the quality of the medical services in Benghazi Medical Center, by identifying the main principles and bases of the medical governance system, as well as the role of this system in improving the quality of the medical services. Therefore, in order to determine the attitudes and opinions of the staff at the Benghazi Medical Center about the effectiveness of these principles and the basis of the medical services quality, this paper adopted on the descriptive analytical approach by studying the regulations and instructions on which the Center depends. The preliminary data collected through the questionnaire prepared for this purpose which included a sample size was 30 respondents of doctors, nurses, and administrators. Thus, the paper showed that the medical governance is not implemented in the Benghazi Medical Center and thus has no effect on improving the quality of the medical services. Accordingly, the researchers recommended the need to implement the system of medical governance in public and private health institutions, as a guarantee to improve the medical services quality, and eliminate financial and administrative corruption in these institutions, which is the main reason for the arrival of medical services in Libya to this extent of low and bad

Keywords: Medical Governance, Hospital Governance, Medical Services Quality, and Benghazi Medical Center.

Introduction

Due to the main objective of any government hospital is to meet the needs of the most vulnerable individuals in societies (Abu-Eid, Drawish, & Aida, 2016), especially those with no large area of private health activities.

While government centers and hospitals are the first refuges for the individual, who is entitled to enjoy the highest quality of medical services as a nominal right of his rights within his community. However, the medical services in Libya are one of the most important indicators of sustainable development (Al-Jedi, 2018), and it is an important criterion to measure the extent of its progress and development. Moreover, it is the right of the citizen in his homeland to enjoy the quality of education, health and housing services and to achieve this, there must be effective control systems on the executive organs of the Libya aimed at ascertaining the extent to which they fulfill their responsibilities, Furthermore, the performance of its duties in the areas of its competence. Also, the implementation of laws and regulations correctly and detect any deviations that may occur (Omar, 2014; Jdiaai, 2017). As well as the disclosure of violations related to the performance of duties of the public office, investigation and taking the necessary measures to face the involved.

According to Abdullah (2017), corporate governance refers to procedures and practices for the direction and control of the institution. Moreover, the distribution of rights and responsibilities among the various participants in the institution - such as the board of directors, managers and shareholders, and other stakeholders. Also, formulate the rules and procedures for decision. Hospitals do not differ in many aspects from other institutions. In addition, the adoption of corporate governance practices, or the so-called modern concept of medical governance, has great benefits, such as achieving quality of performance and developing its services, it also

aims to define the responsibilities of the board and medical staff so that human resources are committed to their professional responsibilities (Akti & Mekkrache, 2012).

In this context, the aim of this study is to identify the role of the medical governance system in achieving the quality of medical services at Benghazi Medical Center through an applied study that will be applied to Benghazi Medical Center. Therefore, the problem of this paper comes in the following questions: What is the role of implementing the medical governance system at Benghazi Medical Center in improving the quality of medical services? To what extent apply Principles of Medical Management at Benghazi Medical Center? And what relationship the application of principles this system improves the quality of medical services?

Furthermore, the Benghazi Medical Center, or "1200 Bed Hospital" as it is also known, It was established in the 1970s and was postponed until the beginning of 2006. It is the largest hospital in the Libyan city of Benghazi. However, in 2007, the Republic of France and the European Union undertook to equip it, complete and manage the center. Moreover, transform it into a regional center, and train medical personnel. Where the first phase of the center was inaugurated in March 2009 (Almabruk, 2017).

Problem Study

Despite the fact that the concept of company governance is closely linked to firms and financial markets, the appliance of this concept within the non-profit sector like health sectors is of great worth. Medical governance offers viable solutions which will scale back the obstacles presently facing hospitals and have an effect on the standard of services provided to patients. the appliance of medical governance and also the principles of revealing can facilitate hospitals - like several different establishments - to be higher structured, a lot of clear, and thus a lot of sure-fire and property, and from this attitude the matter of study is restricted to responsive the subsequent questions:

- i. How much attention is paid to applying the principles of medical governance in hospitals in Libya?
- ii. What is Medical Governance? What are the most principles of its application?
- iii. What is the truth of medical governance in Libya?
- iv. Is there an efficient application of medical governance in health centers in Libya?
- v. Can the medical governance system contribute to rising the of medical services quality if applied in Libyan hospitals?

The importance of the study

The importance of the study stems from the importance of the system of governance normally in its ability stemming from the standards and also the bases upon that it's supported it in reaching the goals that any establishment is doing in a very balanced, clear and clear manner, so achieving the goals with the smallest amount doable deviations. Therefore, the importance of adopting the principles of governance in hospitals. Medical governance can inevitably contribute to making a sound atmosphere for implementation, making certain that goals aren't deviated from what's planned, reducing corruption and eliminating mediation and favoritism through transparency, disclosure, answerableness, and answerableness, thereby making certain higher delivery of medical services.

Study objectives

The most objective of this study is to undertake to spot the role of applying the medical governance system in raising the quality of the medical services in Libyan hospitals by distinguishing the following:

- i. Principles and components of the medical governance system, and concepts associated with raising the quality of the medical services.
- ii. The role of applying the medical governance system in raising the quality of the medical services.

- iii. To what degree do the principles of medical governance apply in Libyan hospitals?
- iv. The relationship of applying the principles of medical governance to rising the medical services quality provided to society.
- v. Whether there's a transparent understanding of the concepts associated with the medical governance system in Libyan hospitals.

Study Model

Literature Review

Researchers and academics are interested in the concept of the system of corporate governance at all levels. The following is a presentation of the most important studies on governance in government institutions, focusing on governance in the health sector:

The study of (Rahima & Klutma, 2013) aimed at identifying the impact of governance standards on their dimensions (transparency, disclosure, the board of directors, information management, and ethics of the medical profession) on the requirements of Total Quality Management (TQM). (Supporting and supporting management, customer orientation, improving the quality of medical services, leadership and participation, organization culture, skills development).

Therefore, this study reached despite the keenness of Algeria to adopt these concepts in modern hospitals, it is still lagging behind the issue of the actual implementation. The study recommended several recommendations, including the need to adopt and apply the standards of governance to ensure the implementation of quality management.

Studied by (Fischer & McGivern, 2011) aimed to identify the reactions on organizational transparency by the staff in the functions of psychotherapy and medicine. The researchers concluded that transparency is a good policy to exercise control by providing rules that are comparable between the fixed rules and visual activities.

And accountability. In the medical profession, transparency has complex effects and practices that lead to the search for excellence so that the employee does not fall within the accountability network. It also leads to the search for ways to continually improve the system as well as to improve the responses to this transparency in order to serve the incumbent.

On the other hand, the two researchers believe that the transparency of the medical profession will create more pressure on practitioners as more accountable to them, as well as create confidence and positive impression in front of officials and colleagues in the job. And believe that the reliance on self-control of the individual make the proportion of accountability by others is small, as well as if the understanding of the requirements of his job and committed to the role to be done, in addition to that he can overcome his limitations when he felt by doing a process of development of his skill, And the researchers believe that the ability of the employee from taking advantage of transparency in this institution will create some kind of commitment and with the direction of time creates has a loyalty to the post held.

The study by (Akti, & Mekkrache, 2012) The study aimed to test the impact of hospital governance on its dimensions of transparency, the board of directors and information management, audit committees, and management of rewards for medical ethics, in terms of self-control, loyalty, accuracy, and clarity. The role, and skills development, applying to Jijel General Hospital. The study concluded that the Jijel Public Hospital applies a high level of governance, and the medical staff has a high level of professional ethics. The results also confirmed that the management of rewards and transparency has a direct positive impact on medical ethics, while the Board of Directors And management Information and audit committees have no direct impact on medical ethics.

The Proprietary Theory

The Proprietary does not constitute a legal guarantor and alone does not perform an economic security function. This new conception of ownership evolves at different historical stages imposed by circumstances surrounding the economic reality. Where Proposes the Proprietary Theory at the core of modern neoclassical approaches Establishments can highlight how different types of property systems can affect the behavior of agents, on the management and effectiveness of the economic system? How are contractual reports between agents free in the economy? The main function of property rights contributed to the incitement factors for creativity and asset evaluation by short use of resources effectively (Nasira, 2018).

Study hypotheses

Through the matter of the study that was reviewed in the above, the subsequent hypotheses were developed:

The first main hypothesis

The null hypothesis: Medical governance principles don't seem to be applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: Medical governance principles are applied in Libyan hospitals.

From this hypothesis, the subsequent sub-hypotheses were formulated:

The first sub-hypothesis

- a) The null hypothesis: The principle of Accountability is not applied in Libyan hospitals.
- b) The alternative hypothesis: The principle of Accountability is applied in Libyan hospitals.

The second sub-hypothesis:

- a) The null hypothesis: The principle of equity and equality is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

- b) The alternative hypothesis: The principle of equity and equality is applied in Libyan hospitals.

The third sub-hypothesis:

- a) The null hypothesis: The principle of participation is not applied in Libyan hospitals.
b) The alternative hypothesis: The principle of participation is applied in Libyan hospitals.

The fourth sub-hypothesis:

- a) The null hypothesis: The principle of respect for the rule of law is not applied in Libyan hospitals.
b) The alternative hypothesis: The principle of respect for the rule of law is applied in Libyan hospitals.

The fifth sub-hypothesis:

- a) The null hypothesis: The principle of effectiveness and efficiency is not applied in Libyan hospitals.
b) The alternative hypothesis: The principle of effectiveness and efficiency is applied in Libyan hospitals.

The sixth sub-hypothesis:

- a) The null hypothesis: The principle of strategic vision is not applied in Libyan hospitals.
b) The alternative hypothesis: The principle of strategic vision is applied in Libyan hospitals.

The seventh sub-hypothesis:

- a) The null hypothesis: The principle of decentralization is not applied in Libyan hospitals.
b) The alternative hypothesis: The principle of decentralization is applied in Libyan hospitals.

The eighth sub-hypothesis:

- a) The null hypothesis: The principle of transparency and disclosure is not applied in Libyan hospitals.
b) The alternative hypothesis: The principle of transparency and disclosure is applied in Libyan hospitals.

The hypothesis of the second major study incorporates a statistically important impact on the contribution of the principles of governance in raising the quality of the medical services.

Data collection tool

In order to achieve the objectives of the study, the questionnaire was used as the main tool for collecting study data. Also, the questionnaire included three main parts: demographic data on participants (experience, qualification, and the job). The second part represents the principles of medical governance. While the third part represents data that reflects the quality of the medical services.

Reliability and Stability coefficients

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was used to confirm the stability of the questionnaire items, and the accuracy coefficient was obtained for the questionnaire axes by taking the square root of the stability coefficient value as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Reliability and Stability coefficients

Variables	No	Stability	Reliability
Principle of accountability	5	0.915	0.956
principle of equity and equality	6	0.898	0.947
Principle of participation	6	0.916	0.957
Principle of respect for the rule of law	4	0.887	0.941
principle of effectiveness and efficiency	6	0.922	0.960
Principle of strategic vision	4	0.904	0.950
Principle of decentralization	4	0.944	0.971
principle of transparency and disclosure	3	0.775	0.880
Total	38	0.977	0.988

According to table 1, the stability coefficient for all axes and items of questionnaires reached 0.977, and the axes (principles of governance) obtained coefficients greater than 0.9. This indicates that the questionnaire data collection tool is Stable and reliable, which can be used with confidence as a valid measurement tool for analysis.

Demographic Data:

Table 2: Demographic Data

	Variable	The ratio
Qualification	Ph.D.	3.3%
	M.A.	10%
	Bachelor	60%
	Average Diploma	26.7%
The Job	A doctor	23.3%
	Nurse	33.3%
	Administrative	26.7%
	Other	16.7%
Experience	Less than 5 years	20%
	From 5 to 10 years	60%
	From 11 to 15 years	6.7%
	More than 15 years	13.3%

Table 2 shows that 60% of the participation in the study has a bachelor's degree or equivalent, followed by 26.7%, which represents the average diploma campaign and its equivalent, and 13.3% of the holders of higher qualifications (Ph.D., MA). These percentages give an indication of the participants' understanding of the study to answer the questionnaire. The table also shows that 33.3% of the participants are nursing staff, followed by 26.7% of the administrative staff of the hospital and 23.3% of the doctors, while 16.7% (other) represent the technical staff of the hospital. Looking at the table, 60% have 5 to 10 years of experience, and 20% have more than 11 years of experience, which increases the level of confidence in respondents' responses.

Analysis of the results of the field study and testing hypotheses:

Used a number of statistical methods suitable for data analysis and access to the objectives of the study through the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The range was calculated using the following formula the largest value (Strongly Agree) – smallest value (Strongly Disagree) divided by 5 or about 0.80. Accordingly, the approval levels will be as shown in Table 3 and will be determined at any of the levels

mentioned in the table contains the mean of the variables of the study (Principles of Medical Governance). Accordingly, the results are analyzed and the hypotheses tested.

Table 3: Scale of approval

Scale of Approval	Measurement Limits	
	Maximum	Minimum
Strongly Disagree	1.79	1
Not Agree	2.59	1.80
Neutral	3.39	2.60
Agree	4.19	3.40
Strongly Agree	5	4.20

Discussion and Analysis of hypotheses

The questionnaire tool contained (48) paragraphs divided into two dimensions. Where the first of these concerns the application of the principles of medical governance at the Medical Center: (Principle of accountability, equity and equality, participation, respect for the rule of law, effectiveness and efficiency, strategic vision, decentralization, and transparency and disclosure). However, the second concerns the contribution of medical governance to the medical center in improving the quality of the medical services. In addition, a one-sample t-test was used to test hypotheses.

Test the first main hypothesis:

The null hypothesis: Medical governance principles are not applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: Medical governance principles are applied in Libyan hospitals.

Thus, to test the main hypothesis first, it has been derived eight sub-hypotheses are as follows:

Test the first sub-hypothesis:

The null hypothesis: The principle of Accountability is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: The principle of Accountability is applied in Libyan hospitals.

Table 4: t test the first sub-hypothesis

Principle of Accountability	Statistical Decision	Std. Deviation	mean	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
The Center has an appropriate system of control and accountability at various administrative levels.	statistically	1.225	2.5	-2.236-	29	.033	-.500-	-.96-	-.04-
The Center provides the appropriate environment for the reception of specialized individuals, bodies, and committees of external control, and look forward to their reports and work.	statistically	1.167	2.47	-2.504-	29	.018	-.533-	-.97-	-.10-
The Center holds and organizes periodic meetings with citizens in which complaints are heard and the violators are held accountable according to the law.	statistically	1.017	2.00	-5.385-	29	.000	-1.000-	-1.38-	-.62-
Any employee or citizen can report any individual and any violation in a clear sequence that ensures his safety and protection and punishes the offender according to the law.	statistically	1.221	2.40	-2.693-	29	.012	-.600-	-1.06-	-.14-
Periodic reports are evaluated by employees and departments of senior management to follow up the work, projects, and plans according to the regulations and correct the errors.	not statistically	2.67	1.184	-1.542-	29	.134	-.333-	-.78-	.11
Total		1.006	2.407	-3.228-	29	.003	-.59333-	-.9693-	-.2174-

Table 4 shows that the mean of the paragraphs of the variable (Principle of Accountability) ranges from (1.184) to (2.5), which is well below the default value (3) We find that the probability values are less than the moral level ($\alpha = 0.5$), which is a statistical function, except the fifth paragraph is not statistically significant, but the negative (t) indicates that t calculated in the acceptance area of null hypothesis (The principle of Accountability is not applied in Libyan hospitals), and the values of the limits of the negative confidence period indicate that the average of the community is less than the default value. Thus, the test supports the acceptance of the null hypothesis: The principle of Accountability is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

Test the second sub-hypothesis:

The null hypothesis: The principle of equity and equality is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: The principle of equity and equality is applied in Libyan hospitals.

Table 5: t test the second sub-hypothesis

principle of equity and equality	Statistical Decision	Std. Deviation	mean	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
The center performs its services according to the needs and requirements of real and necessary.	not statistically	1.192	2.60	-1.838-	29	.076	-.400-	-.85-	.05
The Center takes into consideration the equality of transactions between the genders of doctors and staff of the Center.	statistically	1.224	2.47	-2.386-	29	.024	-.533-	-.99-	-.08-
The Employment Center system includes the need to provide equal opportunity for both genders to compete.	not statistically	1.331	2.57	-1.783-	29	.085	-.433-	-.93-	.06
The Center takes into account the principle of social justice in the design and implementation of its programs and plans.	not statistically	1.273	2.63	-1.578-	29	.125	-.367-	-.84-	.11
The Center provides equal opportunities for both genders to benefit from the training courses of the implemented projects.	not statistically	1.206	2.83	-.757-	29	.455	-.167-	-.62-	.28
The Center is careful to provide services to citizens without discrimination or bias.	not statistically	1.289	2.83	-.708-	29	.484	-.167-	-.65-	.31
Total		1.0198	2.655	-1.850-	29	.075	-.34444-	-.7253-	.0364

The mean of the paragraphs in Table 5 shows that all probability values are greater than the statistical significance level (0.05) except for the second paragraph of the axis, and the average of the axes ranges between (2.47) and (2.83) Indicating that the principle of justice and equality is not effectively applied, as confirmed by the values of negative confidence limits which indicate that the average of the society is less than the default value (3). When calculating the confidence interval for the average of the community by setting the default value to zero, it was found that with a confidence level of 95%, the average society was between (2.27, 3.03). It has been accepted to the null hypothesis: The principle of equity and equality is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

Test the third sub-hypothesis:

The null hypothesis: The principle of participation is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: The principle of participation is applied in Libyan hospitals.

Table 6: t test the third sub-hypothesis

Principle of participation	Statistical Decision	Std. Deviation	mean	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
Decisions are taken at the center by voting and the results of the vote are published along with the reasons for the decision.	statistically	1.061	2.33	-3.440-	29	.002	-.667-	-1.06-	-.27-
The Center holds special meetings with stakeholders and expertise before implementing its own programs and projects to bring together views.	not statistically	1.159	2.63	-1.733-	29	.094	-.367-	-.80-	.07
In defining its vision of implementing development programs and projects, the Center takes the views of the stakeholders.	not statistically	1.179	2.70	-1.394-	29	.174	-.300-	-.74-	.14
The Center shall adhere by the policies of the Ministry of Health, taking into account the strategic objectives of the Center.	not statistically	1.232	3.00	.000	29	1.000	.000	-.46-	.46
The application of the principle of unanimity in the center ensures the achievement of the objectives of development projects.	not statistically	1.172	2.73	-1.246-	29	.223	-.267-	-.70-	.17
The Center adopts the method of consultation and the use of expertise when making central decisions at the Center.	not statistically	1.291	2.70	-1.273-	29	.213	-.300-	-.78-	.18
Total		.9945	2.683	-1.744-	29	.092	-.31667-	-.6880-	.0547

It is clear from Table (3-6) that the average responses of the participants to the points of the participation axis ranged between (2.33 and 3.00). In general, the answers of the participants were average (2.68) and standard deviation (0.994). The moral test also showed that the probability value of the axial segments is greater than 0.05, which means that it has no meaning in practice, except for the first paragraph, although it is a statistical function. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. The principle of participation is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

Test the fourth sub-hypothesis:

The null hypothesis: The principle of respect for the rule of law is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: The principle of respect for the rule of law is applied in Libyan hospitals.

Table 7: t test the fourth sub-hypothesis

Principle of respect for the rule of law	Statistical Decision	Std. Deviation	mean	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
The Center has its own financial and administrative systems to organize its business.	not statistically	1.408	2.87	-.519-	29	.608	-.133-	-.66-	.39
The Center's systems and internal regulations are consistent with its vision and objectives.	not statistically	1.279	2.53	-1.998-	29	.055	-.467-	-.94-	.01
All administrative and financial transactions of the Center shall be carried out in accordance with its internal regulations.	not statistically	1.311	2.93	-.278-	29	.783	-.067-	-.56-	.42
The administration shall abide by the statutes of the Center with regard to the responsibilities of departments managers and electoral and selection mechanisms.	not statistically	1.291	2.70	-1.273-	29	.213	-.300-	-.78-	.18
Total		1.145	2.758	-1.157-	29	.257	-.24167-	-.6687-	.1854

Table 7 shows the results of the T test for the fourth hypothesis. The average of the axles (2.7) has a standard deviation (1.145). The result of the moral test was that the value of $0.05p >$ ranged between (0.055, 0.783). Finally, the null hypothesis is accepted that the principle of respect for the rule of law is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

Test the fifth sub-hypothesis:

The null hypothesis: The principle of effectiveness and efficiency is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: The principle of effectiveness and efficiency is applied in Libyan hospitals.

Table 8: t test the fifth sub-hypothesis

Principle of effectiveness and efficiency	Statistical Decision	Std. Deviation	mean	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
The services provided to the public at the center are adequate and provide services to citizens to the fullest.	statistically	1.276	2.40	-.576-	29	.015	-.600-	-1.08-	-.12-
The Center shall study the resources available to provide its services to ensure optimum utilization.	not statistically	1.155	2.9	-.474-	29	.639	-.100-	-.53-	.33
The Center achieves special and public objectives related to the implementation of programs, plans and development projects.	statistically	1.073	2.57	-2.213-	29	.035	-.433-	-.83-	-.03-
The Center is interested in increasing the cultural and cognitive aspects of its medical staff and employees through special development programs.	not statistically	1.217	2.97	-.150-	29	.882	-.033-	-.49-	.42
The center provides medical and nursing staff at all times.	statistically	1.167	2.47	-2.504-	29	.018	-.533-	-.97-	-.10-
The Center provides according to its capabilities, all necessary health supplies to the public in a timely manner.	statistically	1.184	2.33	-3.084-	29	.004	-.667-	-1.11-	-.22-
Total		1.0014	2.605	-2.157-	29	.039	-.39444-	-.7684-	-.0205-

Table 8 shows the results of the T test for the fifth hypothesis, indicating that the second and fourth paragraphs are not statistically significant, where the value of p respectively was 0.639, 0.882. The first, third, fifth and sixth verbs are statistically significant, with a value of 0.05 p . However, the averages of these paragraphs are in the index (mean application), and the negative t indicates that these paragraphs fall within the acceptance area of the null hypothesis, the values of the negative confidence limits (ie, the mean of the community is less than the default value). When calculating the confidence interval for the average of the community at a default value of zero, it is between 2.23 and 2.97 at 95% confidence level. From the above, the null hypothesis (The principle of effectiveness and efficiency is not applied in Libyan hospitals) is accepted.

Test the sixth sub-hypothesis:

The null hypothesis: The principle of strategic vision is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: The principle of strategic vision is applied in Libyan hospitals.

Table 9: t test the sixth sub-hypothesis

Principle of strategic vision	Statistical Decision	Std. Deviation	mean	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
The Center has a clear and detailed strategic plan.	not statistically	1.066	2.63	-1.884-	29	.070	-.367-	-.76-	.03
Seminars and dialogue sessions with target groups are held consulted and involved them in prioritizing and budgeting.	not statistically	1.251	2.57	-1.898-	29	.068	-.433-	-.90-	.03
The Center has a development plan linked to its strategic objectives.	not statistically	1.194	2.57	-1.987-	29	.056	-.433-	-.88-	.01
The Center identifies opportunities and risks that affect its services.	not statistically	1.278	2.57	-1.857-	29	.073	-.433-	-.91-	.04
Total		1.0572	2.5833	-2.159-	29	.039	-.41667-	-.8115-	-.0219-

Table 9 shows the results of the T test for the sixth hypothesis, where the result of the moral test was not statistically significant for all the axes of the axis, ranged from (0.056, 0.073). According to this the null hypothesis (The principle of strategic vision is not applied in Libyan hospitals) is accepted.

Test the seventh sub-hypothesis:

The null hypothesis: The principle of decentralization is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: The principle of decentralization is applied in Libyan hospitals.

Table 10: t test the seventh sub-hypothesis

Principle of decentralization	Statistical Decision	Std. Deviation	mean	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
The Center has a clear organizational structure and communication lines that prevent overlapping of powers.	not statistically	1.297	2.8	-.844-	29	.405	-.200-	-.68-	.28
The main decisions are made at the center by involving the various departments with the board of directors by the majority.	not statistically	1.053	2.83	-.867-	29	.393	-.167-	-.56-	.23
Management is not unique in making decisions at the center.	statistically	1.073	2.57	-2.213-	29	.035	-.433-	-.83-	-.03-
There is a specific space for each department that allows decisions to be made within certain limits to serve the interests of the work.	not statistically	1.062	2.9	-.516-	29	.610	-.100-	-.50-	.30
Total		0.9292	2.775	-1.326-	29	.195	-.22500-	-.5720-	.1220

Table 10 shows that the axis of (decentralization) has a mean of 2.775 and a standard deviation (0.9371). All the pivot clauses are not statistically significant. It is also shown by calculated t values. Wherefore, the null hypothesis (The principle of decentralization is not applied in Libyan hospitals) is accepted.

Test the eighth sub-hypothesis:

The null hypothesis: The principle of transparency and disclosure is not applied in Libyan hospitals.

The alternative hypothesis: The principle of transparency and disclosure is applied in Libyan hospitals.

Table 11: t test the eighth sub-hypothesis

Principle of transparency and disclosure	Statistical Decision	Std. Deviation	mean	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
The Center publishes its financial and management reports on a regular and public basis, clarifying its activities to the relevant authorities and providing any information needed.	statistically	1.221	2.40	-2.693-	29	.012	-.600-	-1.06-	-.14-
The Center has a website with all the information and mechanisms for making future plans.	not statistically	1.157	2.80	-.947-	29	.351	-.200-	-.63-	.23
The Center has a written complaint system for the employees and citizens and complaints and suggestions are processed.	statistically	0.997	2.20	-4.397-	29	.000	-.800-	-1.17-	-.43-
Total		0.9371	2.4667	-3.117-	29	.004	-.53333-	-.8833-	-.1834-

Table 11 shows that the second paragraph is not statistically significant where P is greater than 0.05, and the first and third paragraphs of the transparency and disclosure axis are statistically significant. P is less than 0.05, respectively (2.40, 2.20) and it falls within the scope of a weak application level indicator. The calculated t values fall within the scope of the null hypothesis acceptance area. When calculating the confidence interval for the average of the community by setting the default value to zero and a significant level of 0.000, with a confidence level of 95%, the average of the society is (2.116, 2.81). The null hypothesis of the eighth sub-hypothesis (The principle of transparency and disclosure is not applied in Libyan) is accepted.

However, and based on the acceptance of the null hypotheses of the sub-hypotheses of the first main hypothesis. Therefore, the null hypothesis of the first main hypothesis (The principles of medical governance are not applied in Libyan hospitals) is accepted.

Test the second main hypothesis

“There is a significant effect on the application of the principles of medical governance at the Center in improving the quality of the medical services”.

Table 12: t test the second main hypothesis

Principle of transparency and disclosure	Statistical Decision	Std. Deviation	mean	Test Value = 3					
				t	df	Sig.	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
								Lower	Upper
The application of the principles of medical governance at the Center effects the improving the quality of the medical services.	not statistically	1.06	2.600	-1.981-	29	.057	-.40000-	-.8130-	.0130

Table 12 shows the result of the test of the second main hypothesis using the t test for one sample. Where P is greater than 0.05. Accordingly, the second main hypothesis is rejected, and it is clear that there is no effect on the application of the principles of medical governance at the Center in improving the quality of the medical services.

Conclusion

Medical governance principles are not applied in Libyan hospitals. As well, there is no effect on the application of the principles of medical governance at the Center in improving the quality of the medical services. Moreover, there is a lack of awareness of the importance of the system of medical governance among Libyan

hospital staff. There is also no clear guide of the functioning of Libyan hospitals. In addition, there is also no real and effective control of wrong practices such as job neglect. Finally, there are no clear items that regulate accountability, transparency, and equity, where this can only be achieved through the activation of the medical governance system.

According to the results of this paper, the principles of governance in public and private health institutions must be activated as a guarantee to improve the quality of medical services. To increase awareness of the concept of governance in general, and medical governance in particular, through courses, conferences, research and human resource development in health institutions.

Moreover, develop medical services, improve their quality, and reduce financial and administrative corruption. Accordingly, the establishment of special committees to develop and follow up the legislation and regulations on medical governance, which is subordinate to the Ministry of Health so that it has more independence for its work. Preparation of further studies on the medical governance system, And the most important characteristics them, and how to apply it in the Libyan environment. As well as knowledge of the most important obstacles that can cause a lack of not effective if applied.

Contribution

Accounting literature is rich in studies on corporate governance in several aspects, in terms of improving performance, competitive advantage, solving the crisis, reducing corruption of all kinds.

However, the studies related to medical governance - hospital governance is very scarce, both at the regional or international level, despite the high voices calling for the application and importance of the reform of the health sector, and improve the quality of services.

While this paper focused on the role that the system of medical governance in Libya can play in improving the quality of the medical services, especially with the situation in the country, and the suffering of this sector from the deterioration of its services and many problems, due to the this conditions.

However, this paper can provide solutions to these problems. And to alleviate the crises suffered by the health sector in Libya, especially this paper is the first of its kind in the Libyan environment, according to researchers.

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